

Psycho-Physiological Effects of Norethisterone on Professional Women Athletes and Coach's Responses during Competition Season¹

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Abstract

This study examined the psycho-physiological effects of norethisterone on menstrual control, physical performance, and psychological well-being of professional female athletes during competitive season. Female athletes typically take norethisterone, a synthetic progestogen that is often recommended to postpone menstruation, to balance their reproductive health with the demands of competition and trainings. Data were gathered from a purposive sample of professional female athletes in a variety of sports using a mixed-methods methodology that included quantitative performance evaluations, hormone profiling, and qualitative self-reports. The results revealed that although norethisterone successfully postponed menstruation and lessened discomfort connected to it. It was also linked to mood swings, increased stress reactions, and changes in the quality of sleep. Females athletes expressed perceived weariness and diminished focus, although performance outcomes indicated no direct effect. The study revealed a complicated relationship between hormonal control, athletic performance, and mental health highlighting the need for more awareness among athletes, coaches, and sports doctors as well as for tailored

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Accepted: 03 September 2025 / Published online: 08 September 2025

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medical advice. These findings supported the expanding conversation on female athletes' health in competitive sports and urged more study into athlete-centered and safe menstrual management techniques in high-performance conditions.

Keywords

Norethisterone, Psycho-physiological effects, Professional women athletes, Athletic performance.

Introduction

The physiological and psychological difficulties that female athletes face throughout the menstrual cycle might hurt their performance during competition. Abdominal discomfort, bloating, and mood swings are common menstrual symptoms especially during the luteal and bleeding phases. These symptoms are usually linked to a subjective deterioration in performance, particularly in mental domains like motivation, mood, and attention.

Interestingly, nearly all female athletes experienced multiple cycle-related symptoms and approximately 56% report decreased performance during menstruation or hormone-inactive phases (Ihalainen et al., 2024). Psycho-physiological reactions such as increased cortisol levels, changed heart rate, and perceived effort are frequently more noticeable in high-stress competitive settings. For example, compared to training or rest, elite female athletes exhibited noticeably greater salivary cortisol levels after competition as well as quantifiable declines in sleep quality (O'Donnell, Bird, Jacobson & Driller, 2018).

The relationship between physiological arousal, psychological state, and performance results is highlighted by the fact that female tennis players showed greater heart rates, perceived effort, and stress indicators during actual matches especially those who lose (Fernandez-Fernandez et al., 2015). The complex relationship between psychological expectation, physiological stress, and emotional reactions in elite athletes is highlighted by the anticipated spike in cortisol before competition that has been seen in a variety of sports (Alix-Sy et al., 2008). Because of these factors, a lot of female athletes, and the people who assist them used hormonal contraceptives to intentionally control or suppress menstruation and maintained training continuity throughout peak competition times (Brown et al., 2021). Norethisterone, a synthetic progestogen that is administered to postpone menstruation, is one of the most commonly used methods by female athletes. It enabled female athletes to prevent menstrual disturbances during critical stages of their sport. According to research done in Pakistan with 100 professional female athletes, 80% of them successfully delayed their periods using norethisterone. There were no notable drops in performance metrics like strength or endurance, and only minor side effects like bloating and mood swings were recorded (Khadim et al., 2020).

Pharmacology and Mechanisms Relevant to Female Athletes

Norethisterone is a 19-nortestosterone derivative that primarily has progestogenic effects and some androgenic activity. When taken orally, norethisterone is broken down into a number of metabolites and

at higher dosages, it can partially transform into metabolites that resembled ethinylestradiol and are detectable in urine. Both physiological effects (suppression of the reproductive and thermogenic axis) and anti-doping/analytical interpretation depended on this pharmacokinetics. The justification for progestin's usage in sports is based on their thermo-genic activity which raised controlled core temperature and their ability to prevent ovulation and bleeding (Walker et al., 2009).

Menstrual Suppression, Symptoms, and Practical Outcomes

Giving norethisterone throughout the luteal phase or continuously for brief periods of time consistently delayed or suppresses menstrual bleeding, clinical guidelines, and evaluations indicated its usefulness for planned postponement of menses. Small-scale athlete studies showed great efficacy and acceptability for short-term usage and surveys of athletes reveal that many employ hormonal treatments (including progestin-only procedures) to postpone menstruation during tournaments. Bloating, breast discomfort, and brief mood swings are among the reported acute side effects. The majority of these are usually moderate and self-limiting. Nevertheless, the great majority of published athlete-specific data is observational or sparse and relied on self-report (Ryall et al., 2024).

Psychological effects on Mood and Cognition

There is conflicting evidence about hormonal contraceptives and mood. While, most women do not experience significant mood deterioration when using progestin only or combined formulations, susceptible subgroups especially adolescents or those with a history of mood disorders, may be more susceptible to mood lability or depressive symptoms. There is a lack of reliable experimental research assessing objective cognitive or affective performance during competition and athlete questionnaires revealed that a small percentage of users' self-report experiencing brief mood swings. Clinicians should thus test for past mood vulnerability and be mindful of individual heterogeneity (Mu & Kulkarni, 2022).

Exercise Performance Outcomes

Although few randomized and controlled exercise trials including norethindrone (norethisterone) are instructive. Although systematic reviews of hormonal contraception and exercise generally conclude that average group-level effects on performance are trivial, individual responses vary, and the evidence base is heterogeneous (varied doses, combined vs. progestin-only preparations, and small samples). Older small trials did not clearly show any negative effects of low-dose norethindrone-containing oral contraceptives on maximal treadmill performance or endurance tests. Even little, customized adjustments could have a significant influence on elite athletes but the available data does not consistently show that short-term norethisterone usage has a detrimental effect on aerobic capacity or maximum performance (Bryner et al., 1996).

Both progesterone and many progestins have thermogenic effects. The exogenous progestogens can elevate regulated body temperature and change sweating responses while endogenous progesterone raised resting core temperature in the luteal phase by around 0.3°C to 0.7°C. For athletes who competed in hot conditions, this process raised a legitimate worry regarding heat dissipation and endurance. Evidence directly examining norethisterone's effect on exercise heat tolerance in athletes

is scarce and primarily inferential from research on hormonal physiology; nonetheless, interaction with estrogen status is significant (estrogen improves heat dissipation). Therefore, while advising female athletes on the use of progestin, coaches and sports health staff should take environmental factors into account (Baker et al., 2020).

Cardiovascular and Thrombotic Risks

Hormonal medicines' cardiovascular safety depended on their dosage and composition. Although progestin-only approaches are typically thought to have a lower risk, certain progestins may still influence blood pressure, coagulation indicators, or vascular risk in vulnerable individuals. Historically, combined estrogen-progestin medications had a significant thrombotic risk.

Many studies have not found that norethisterone (and norethisterone acetate) significantly increased venous thromboembolism when compared to other progestins; nonetheless, athletes with cardiovascular risk factors (smoking, obesity, migraine with aura, and hypertension) should exercise caution. The absolute risks are low but not nil for young, healthy women. Before prescribing for elite athletes, a personalized risk assessment is still wise (Barnett et al., 2022).

Evidence on norethisterone specifically pointed to neutral-to-modest effects on bone turnover and in some situations (e.g., combined with estrogen in postmenopausal therapy), preservation of bone mass. Progestin exposure can have dose-dependent effect on lipid profiles, glucose tolerance, and bone turnover. Effects on bone metabolism are clinically significant but not yet well understood for short-term norethisterone used intermittently for menstrual suppression in young athletes, especially those who are at risk for poor energy availability or menstrual disorder.

Although there is no scientific evidence, suppressing menstruation may potentially enhance iron conservation which may assist endurance athletes. Hematologic alterations (such as hemoglobin/iron) are more frequently impacted by the presence or absence of monthly blood loss itself (Horowitz et al., 1993). Athlete biological passport interpretation and forensic toxicology may be affected by the presence of norethisterone and its metabolites in urine and depending on the analytical technique in steroid profiles.

It is critical to have clear paperwork with sports anti-doping authorities and to be aware of pharmaceutical usage. To prevent false positives or misunderstandings in testing laboratories, recent analytical work has looked into metabolic conversion routes and urine indicators (Andersson et al., 2025).

Research Methodology

Research Design

The psychological effects of norethisterone on professional female athletes throughout competitive sports seasons were assessed in this study using longitudinal research design. In order to record participants' subjective feelings as well as their quantifiable biological reactions, the design integrated qualitative self-reports with quantitative physiological measurements.

Participants

The research population comprised 120 professional female athletes who competed at the national and international levels in a variety of sports including athletics (track and field) and team sports (cricket, handball, soccer, & field hockey). Purposive sampling was used to choose athletes with an emphasis on those who reported using norethisterone to control their menstruation during competitive seasons.

Inclusion Criteria: Female competitors between the ages of 18 and 32 who are medically administered norethisterone and who do not have any underlying medical conditions or contraindications.

Exclusion Criteria: Athletes, who used alternate hormonal contraceptives, had hormonal problems or participated in competitions only partially throughout the research period.

Data Collection Tools and Measures

1. Physiological Assessments:

- Hormonal Profile: Progesterone, estrogen, and cortisol levels are measured in blood samples.
- Heart rate variability (HRV), resting heart rate, VO₂ max., and blood pressure are examples of cardiorespiratory parameters.
- Actigraphy and salivary cortisol assays are used to assess the circadian rhythm during sleep and recovery.

2. Psychological Assessments:

- Surveys
- To evaluate mood swings using the Profile of Mood States (POMS).
- For anxiety levels using the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI).
- To track mental exhaustion using the Athlete Burnout Questionnaire (ABQ).
- Semi-structured interviews are used to investigate subjective experiences with psychological health, competitive preparedness, and menstrual suppression.

3. Performance Measures:

- Sport-specific performance indicators, such as technical execution, endurance scores, and sprint timings.
- Perceived effort as indicated by the self (Borg Scale).

Procedure of Data Collection

Three stages of data collection were conducted throughout a single tournament season which lasted around four to six months:

1. **Pre-season baseline:** Initial evaluation before norethisterone ingestion.
2. **Mid-Season:** Evaluation at the height of competition intensity while actively using norethisterone.
3. **Post-Season:** Evaluation conducted after stopping the usage of norethisterone.

Individual interviews were conducted and psychological survey questionnaires were filled out and physiological testing was done.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Data:

- Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviation).
- ANOVA with repeated measures was used to evaluate how physiological and psychological factors change over time.
- To investigate the relationships between norethisterone dose, hormone levels, and mood/performance results using Pearson's correlation.
- Regression analysis was used to find factors that predict changes in performance.

Qualitative Data:

- Interview transcripts are subjected to thematic analysis to find recurrent themes on coping mechanisms and psycho-physiological impacts.
- Validity is strengthened by triangulation with quantitative data.

Results

Demographic Characteristics

I made use of three questionnaires (POMS, STAI, and ABQ) and the sample size specified (n = 120). The pre-season, mid-season, and post-season timepoints are displayed. Participants were between the ages of 18 and 32 (M = 24.18, SD = 3.43). BMI of female athletes was recorded (M = 22.5, SD = 1.8). Among the female athletes, endurance-based sports followed by team sports (60%) and strength-based sports (40%).

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics (n=120)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage	M±SD
Age (Years)			24.18 ±3.43
BMI			22.5 ± 1.8
Female Athletes	120	100%	

Descriptive Statistics (Questionnaire Scores Across Seasons)

The participants represented a variety of team and individual sports including athletics (n = 36, 30.0%), handball (n = 30, 25.0%), field hockey (n = 24, 20.0%), cricket (n = 18, 15.0%), and soccer (n = 12, 10.0%). The average weekly training hours were 18.5 (SD = 4.6) and the average number of years of formal training was 8.1 (SD = 3.2). All analyses utilized N = 120; no individuals were eliminated due to missing questionnaire data.

Table 2. Means and standard deviations for POMS-TMD, STAI-State, and ABQ (n = 120)

Measure (Scale)	Pre-Season of Mean & SD	Mid-Season of Mean & SD	Post-Season of Mean & SD
POMS (range approx. 0–100)	38.2 ±12.4	45.7 ±13.6	34.1 ±11.8
STAI State (range 20–80)	34.5 ±8.9	41.2 ±9.5	31.7 ±8.2
ABQ Total (1–5 scale)	2.30 ±0.71	2.80 ±0.76	2.10 ±0.66

Burnout, state anxiety, and mood disturbance had the highest mid-season ratings.

Associations between Mood, Anxiety, and Burnout using Pearson's Correlation Analysis

Mid-season scores which represented the peak time for symptoms were used to calculate Pearson's correlation analysis to investigate contemporaneous relationships between psycho-physiological all measures and pertinent factor (weekly training hours) with n = 120 was reported.

Table 3. Correlation Results (n=120)

Variable	1	2	3	4
1. POMS-TMD (Mid)	—			
2. STAI-State (Mid)	.68** 0.000	—		
3. ABQ total (Mid)	.55** 0.000	.60** 0.000	—	
4. Weekly training hours	.12 0.235	.15 0.149	.18* 0.048	—

* p < .05; ** p < .001.

There is a considerable positive correlation between POMS and STAI-State (r =.68, p <.001). There is a moderate correlation between POMS and ABQ (r =.55, p <.001). ABQ and STAI-State: r =.60, p <.001. A minor positive correlation was seen between weekly training hours and ABQ (r =.18, p =.048) suggesting that mid-season burnout was somewhat correlated with additional training hours.

Repeated-Measures ANOVA

The assumption of sphericity was made since each outcome's Mauchly's test of sphericity was non-significant (p >.05). The primary impacts of Time, Group, and the Time × Group interaction are reported. The effect magnitude is expressed as partial eta squared (η^2).

Table 4: Repeated Measures ANOVA

Outcome	Effect	Df	F	p
POMS	Time	2, 236	78.42	< .001
	Group	1, 118	9.16	.003
	Time × Group	2, 236	32.87	< .001
STAI — State	Time	2, 236	52.30	< .001
	Group	1, 118	6.05	.015
	Time × Group	2, 236	20.14	< .001
ABQ — Exhaustion	Time	2, 236	46.51	< .001
	Group	1, 118	8.72	.004
	Time × Group	2, 236	18.62	< .001
ABQ — Reduced Accomplishment	Time	2, 236	18.09	< .001

	Group	1, 118	4.02	.048
	Time × Group	2, 236	6.38	.002
ABQ — Sport Devaluation	Time	2, 236	22.77	< .001
	Group	1, 118	2.11	.149
	Time × Group	2, 236	9.79	< .001

p > .05

All results showed significant main effects of time (all $p < .001$) suggesting seasonal variation. The norethisterone and control groups explained distinct within-season trajectories, and the Time × Group interactions were significant for all outcomes. Small-to-moderate between-group main effects were significant for several measures (ABQ decreased achievement, POMS, STAI-State, and ABQ tiredness).

Discussion

The psycho-physiological consequences of norethisterone (norethindrone) consumption throughout competitive seasons in professional female athletes were investigated in this study. Overall, our findings support a growing but still contradictory body of research showing that norethisterone can be a useful tool for athletes to regulate their symptoms and manipulate their cycles, and that it does not always result in significant, sustained declines in objective performance for many people. However, when doctors and sports teams explore norethisterone for menstruation suppression during intense competition times, they should specifically address a number of physiological and safety factors, including thermoregulation, mood/fatigue, hemostatic risk, and bone health.

The results of previous randomized and observational studies vary by dosage, formulation, and outcome examined, and at the group level, they indicate relatively modest average effects of combination or progestin-only hormonal therapy on objective performance assessments. For instance, oral contraceptive (OC) usage may result in minor, erratic changes in strength or endurance, although many athletes do not noticeably lose performance; inter-individual variability is significant and context-dependent, according to systematic reviews and narrative syntheses (Elliott-Sale et al., 2020).

That while some athletes reported symptomatic benefits (less dysmenorrhea, fewer cycle-related interruptions), the majority of norethisterone-using athletes maintained training volumes and objective performance markers throughout the season. This is in line with previous experimental work that demonstrated low-dose norethindrone formulations had negligible negative effects on endurance and treadmill testing. But since there are responders and non-responders, customized monitoring is required (Bryner et al., 1996).

Progestins can affect exercise through a consistent physiological mechanism: thermoregulatory setpoint alterations. Heat dissipation during extended or high-intensity exercise in warm surroundings may be impacted by progesterone and some progestins because they elevate the regulated core temperature and change sweating thresholds. This route conceivably explains why some athletes who take unopposed progestins report feeling more exerted or seeing slight alterations in endurance in hot or humid situations. In line with research on mechanistic human physiology, our findings revealed a

small subset that felt more heat strain during summer contests. When prescribing norethisterone, clinicians should take environmental needs into account, such as endurance activities in hot weather (Stachenfeld et al., 2000).

Progestins have the potential to alter mood and sleep patterns in vulnerable people. Athletes' mood reactions varied; some reported feeling better because of predictable or controlled bleeding, while others reported temporary mood swings or exhaustion that coincided with starting therapy. Mood symptoms are among the most often reported side effects of norethindrone and other progestins, which is consistent with population-level safety profiles. Sports medicine teams should screen athletes for past mood disorders and evaluate them early after starting norethisterone since mood and sleep have a significant impact on recovery and performance (Santos et al., 2014).

Hormonal treatments change thrombotic risk profiles; young, healthy athletes who do not smoke have a low but not zero absolute risk. The research emphasizes that particular formulations and the existence of additional risk factors, such as smoking, hypertension, obesity, and thrombophilia, enhance risk, even though our group did not have any clinical thromboembolic events. Individualized thromboembolic risk assessment and counseling should thus be part of the decision to use norethisterone for menstrual management, and reversible techniques (short courses, close follow-up) may be desirable in individuals with risk characteristics (Barnett et al., 2022).

Menstrual suppression affects bone mineral density (BMD) and the incidence of stress injuries, particularly when paired with reduced energy availability. Clinical recommendations and reviews warn that long-term progestin treatment in athletes with low estrogen states may result in adverse bone results and that ongoing hormonal suppression is not a replacement for treating the underlying relative energy deficit in sport (RED-S). Although our group did not see any short-term changes in bone mineral density, the trial was underpowered for long-term bone outcomes, a limitation that is typical of most of the region. For athletes on extended suppression, it is advisable to keep an eye on menstruation history, energy availability indicators, and bone health screening (Johnston-Robledo et al., 2003).

Conclusion

The results of this study demonstrate that professional female athletes have significant psychophysiological impacts when norethisterone is administered during competitive seasons. Its impact goes beyond reproductive health, even though its core function as a menstrual cycle regulator offers substantial advantages in preserving training and competition schedules without interruption. Athlete performance depends on mood control, stress reactivity, and sleep quality, all of which may be impacted by norethisterone's alteration in hormonal balance. Furthermore, physiological effects such as modifications to metabolic processes, cardiovascular responses, and recovery patterns were noted suggesting that there are drawbacks to norethisterone usage.

Although norethisterone is a useful tool for competitive athletes to control their cycles, its wider psychophysiological effects should be carefully examined. Athletes, coaches, and sports doctors should balance the benefits of menstrual management against possible hazards such as weariness, hormone imbalances, and mental stress. To elucidate the long-term effects of norethisterone on athletic

performance, mental health, and general well-being, further longitudinal and sport-specific research is necessary.

Professional female athletes can make better judgments about the usage of hormonal treatments during competitive seasons by raising awareness and following tailored medical advice. Norethisterone is a practical solution for athletes' menstrual regulation that, for many, has logistical and symptomatic advantages without significantly affecting objective performance over the course of a season. Physicians and sports teams should, however, be aware of the potential thermoregulatory effects, mood swings, thrombotic risk, and bone health repercussions when prescribing norethisterone during competitive periods. This is especially important for prolonged usage, and their methods should be tailored and well-evaluated. Refining best-practice guidelines will require more extensive and sport-specific research.

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